

On The Interpolation Concept For Hardy- Orlicz Spaces

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Abstract

The Hardy-Orlicz space H_ϕ is the space of all analytic functions f on the open unit disk D such that the subharmonic function $\phi(|f|)$ has a harmonic majorant on D , where ϕ is a modulus function.

H_ϕ^+ is the subspace of H_ϕ consisting of all $f \in H_\phi$ such that $\phi(|f|)$ has a quasi-bounded harmonic majorant on D . If $\phi(x) = x^p$, $0 < p \leq 1$, then H_ϕ is the Hardy space H^p and if $\phi(x) = \log(1 + x)$, then H_ϕ is the Nevanlinna class N and H_ϕ^+ is the Smirnov class N^+ . In this paper we generalize some of N. Yanagihara's and A. Hartmann's and others interpolation results from N and N^+ to H_ϕ and H_ϕ^+ . For that purpose we generalize a canonical factorization theorem to functions in H_ϕ or H_ϕ^+ and introduce an F-space of complex sequences.

Introduction

If ϕ is a real-valued function on $[0, \infty)$ such that ϕ is increasing, subadditive, $\phi(x) = 0$ iff $x = 0$, and continuous at zero from the right (hence uniformly continuous on $[0, \infty)$), then ϕ is called a *modulus function*. Examples of modulus functions are x^p , $0 < p \leq 1$, and $\log(1 + x)$. We note that the composition of two modulus functions is a modulus function and if ϕ is a modulus function, then $\phi(|\alpha x|) \leq ([|\alpha|] + 1)\phi(|x|)$ for all x in the real numbers \mathbf{R} and for all α in the complex numbers \mathbf{C} ; where $[x]$ is the greatest integer in x .

Let D be the open unit disk in the complex plane \mathbf{C} and H be the space of all analytic functions in D . Throughout this paper we assume that ϕ is a strictly increasing unbounded modulus function such that $\phi(|f|)$ is subharmonic on D for all $f \in H$. The *Hardy-Orlicz space* H_ϕ is the space of all $f \in H$ such that $\phi(|f|)$ has a *harmonic majorant* on D , i.e., there is a function u harmonic on D such that $\phi(|f(z)|) \leq u(z)$ for all $z \in D$. It follows that [8] for each $f \in H_\phi$, $\phi(|f|)$ has a *least harmonic*

majorant u_f , i.e., $\phi(|f(z)|) \leq u_f(z)$, for all $z \in D$ and $u_f(z) \leq v(z)$ for all $z \in D$, where v is any harmonic majorant of $\phi(|f|)$. A non-negative harmonic function on D is called *quasi-bounded* if it is the pointwise increasing limit of non-negative bounded harmonic functions on D . The *Hardy-Orlicz space* H_ϕ^+ is the space of all $f \in H_\phi$ such that $\phi(|f|)$ has a quasi-bounded harmonic majorant on D .

The Hardy-Orlicz spaces H_ϕ and H_ϕ^+ were studied by W. Deeb and M. Marzuq in [2]. M. Masri in [8] and [10] considered these spaces when D is replaced by a domain Ω in \mathbb{C} . Special cases of these spaces were studied by several authors. (See, for example, [3], [4], [9], [11], [3]).

If $\phi(x) = x^p, 0 < p \leq 1$, then $H_\phi = H^p$ and if $\phi(x) = \log(1 + x)$, then $H_\phi = N$ and $H_\phi^+ = N^+$. Also, if $\phi(x) = (\log(1 + x))^p, 0 < p \leq 1$, then $H_\phi = N^p$, and if $\phi(x) = \log(1 + x^p), 0 < p \leq 1$, then $H_\phi = N_p$.

We note that the space H^∞ of bounded analytic functions in D is contained in H_ϕ^+ .

If z_0 is a fixed point in D , which is called the *point of reference*, then the *quasi-norm* $\| \cdot \|_\phi$ on H_ϕ is defined by

$$\|f\|_\phi = u_f(z_0)$$

for all $f \in H_\phi$. If $d(f, g) = \|f - g\|_\phi$ for all $f, g \in H_\phi$, then (H_ϕ, d) is a metric space. If ϕ is a strictly increasing unbounded modulus function, then (H_ϕ^+, d) is an *F-space*, i.e., a topological vector space with complete translation invariant metric (See [1], [2]).

Let $T = \partial D$ be the *boundary* of the open unit disk D in the complex plane \mathbb{C} and H^+ be the set of all functions $f \in H$ such that

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow 1^-} f(re^{i\theta}) = f^*(e^{i\theta}) \text{ exists a. e. } \sigma,$$

where σ is the *normalized Lebesgue measure* on T . The function f^* is called the *radial limit* of f .

When there is no ambiguity we denote the function f and its radial limit by f . The *Hardy-Orlicz spaces* H_ϕ and

H_ϕ^+ , are given by

$$H_\phi = \{f \in H: \sup_{0 \leq r < 1} \int_T \phi(|f_r|) d\sigma < \infty\}$$

And

$$H_\phi^+ = \{f \in H^+: \sup_{0 \leq r < 1} \int_T \phi(|f_r(z)|) d\sigma(z) = \int_T \phi(|f(z)|) d\sigma(z) < \infty\},$$

Where $f_r(z) = f(rz), z \in T \cup D$. [8]

For each $f \in H_\phi$, the quasi-norm of f is given by

$$\|f\|_\phi = u_f(0) = \sup_{0 \leq r < 1} \int_T \phi(|f_r|) d\sigma = \lim_{r \rightarrow 1^-} \int_T \phi(|f_r|) d\sigma$$

And for each $f \in H_\phi^+$

$$\|f\|_\phi = \int_T \phi(|f|) d\sigma. \text{ (See[8])}$$

Moreover, $f \in H_\phi^+$ iff $u_f = P[\phi(|f|)]$, where P denotes the Poisson kernel.

Using Harnack's inequality, it follows that:

$$\phi(|f(z)|) \leq \frac{2\|f\|_\phi}{1-|z|} \text{ for all } f \in H_\phi \text{ and } z \in D. \text{ (See [10]).}$$

Thus, if a sequence $\{f_n\}$ converges to f in H_ϕ or H_ϕ^+ , then it converges uniformly to f on compact subsets of D .

Let $\Lambda = (\lambda_n)$ be a sequence in D such that $\sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|) < \infty$. If Λ has non-zero terms, m is a non-negative integer and

$$B(z) = z^m \prod_{n=1}^\infty \left(\frac{|\lambda_n|}{\lambda_n} \right) \left(\frac{\lambda_n - z}{1 - \lambda_n z} \right), z \in D$$

then the function B is called a *Blaschke product*. The term *Blaschke product* will also be used if there are only finitely many factors of B .

In section 2 of this paper, we give a canonical factorization theorem for functions in H_ϕ or H_ϕ^+ when ϕ is a strictly increasing unbounded modulus function which is a generalization of the special cases $\phi(x)=x^p$, $0 < p \leq 1$ and $\phi(x) = \log(1 + x)$. Other similar canonical factorization theorems involving Blaschke products, singular inner functions and outer functions are still open problems even when ϕ is *strongly modulus*, which is defined in [2] as a modulus function satisfying $\int_1^\infty \frac{\phi(x)}{x^2} dx < \infty$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\phi(x)}{\log x} > 0$ and $\phi(|f|)$ is subharmonic on D for all $f \in H$. Some consequences of the constraint

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\phi(x)}{\log x} = \alpha \in [0, \infty] \text{ on } H_\phi \text{ and } H_\phi^+ \text{ are given in section 4 of this paper.}$$

When $\Lambda = (\lambda_n)$ is a sequence of distinct points in D such that

$$\sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|) < \infty$$

we introduce the following class of complex sequences:

$$\ell_\Lambda(\phi) = \{(c_n): \sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n|) < \infty\}$$

If $\phi(x)=x^p$, $0 < p \leq 1$, then $\ell_\Lambda(\phi) = \ell_\Lambda^p$ and if $\phi(x) = \log(1 + x)$, then $\ell_\Lambda(\phi) = \ell_\Lambda^+$. For these special cases one can see [15] and [16] where $\Lambda = (\lambda_n) = (z_n) = Z$.

In section 3 of this paper we proved that $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ is an F-space. Also, when $\phi(ab) \leq \phi(a) + \phi(b)$, $a, b \geq 0$, we give a characterization of the bounded subsets of $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$, a generalization to that of ℓ_Λ^+ in [16].

A space ℓ of complex sequences is called an *ideal* if $\ell^\infty \ell \subseteq \ell$, i.e., $(w_n c_n) \in \ell$ whenever $(w_n) \in \ell^\infty$ and $(c_n) \in \ell$. Let $\Lambda = (\lambda_n)$ be sequence in D and X a space of analytic functions in D . The *interpolation problem* consists of describing the *trace* $X|\Lambda = \{(f(\lambda_n): f \in X)\}$ of X on Λ .

One approach is to fix a *target space* ℓ and look for conditions so that $X|\Lambda = \ell$. Another approach is to require that $X|\Lambda$ is an ideal and call Λ a *free interpolating sequence* for X . We denote this by $\Lambda \in \text{Int}(X)$.

For certain spaces such as the Hardy and Bergman spaces, the two approaches of interpolation are equivalent with ℓ as an ℓ^p with the appropriate weight (See [5]).

For any function algebra X containing the constants it is easily seen that [5] $\ell^\infty \subseteq X|\Lambda$ iff $\Lambda \in \text{Int}(X)$. This implies that if Y is a subalgebra of a function algebra X , then $\Lambda \in \text{Int}(X)$ whenever $\Lambda \in \text{Int}(Y)$.

Free interpolation for H_ϕ and H_ϕ^+ requires the existence of nonzero functions vanishing on all the terms of the sequence Λ except one. Thus, we assume that $\sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|) < \infty$.

The linear operators T and T_ϕ , given by:

$$Tf = (f(\lambda_n)) \text{ and}$$

$$T_\phi f = \left(\frac{f(\lambda_n)}{\phi^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{1-|\lambda_n|^2}\right)} \right)$$

For all $f \in H_\phi$, are related to interpolation We note that $X|\Lambda = \{(f(\lambda_n): f \in X)\} = T(X)$. When $\phi(x) = x^p, 0 < p \leq 1$, T_ϕ is the operator T_p in [3, Theorem 9.1], where it is shown that $T_p(H^p) = \ell^p, 0 < p \leq \infty, T_\infty = T$, iff (λ_n) is *uniformly separated (Carleson sequence)*. i.e., there exists $\delta > 0$ such that

$$\prod_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq n}}^\infty \left| \frac{\lambda_m - \lambda_n}{1 - \bar{\lambda}_m \lambda_n} \right| \geq \delta, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Some of the interpolation techniques of N. Yanagihara in [17] for N and N^+ carry over to H_ϕ and H_ϕ^+ . A. Hartmann's characterizations of free interpolation in [5] are based on the canonical factorization of functions in N and N^+ in terms of Blaschke products, singular inner functions and outer functions which is not available in H_ϕ and H_ϕ^+ in general.

In section 4 of this paper, we extend some of their results to H_ϕ and H_ϕ^+ and give some consequences in interpolation under certain restrictions on ϕ .

Finally, the following version of the dominated convergence theorem [12] is found out to be useful:

Let $\{g_n\}$ be a sequence of integrable functions which converges a.e. to an integrable function g . Let $\{f_n\}$ be a sequence of measurable functions such that $|f_n| \leq g_n$ and $\{f_n\}$ converges to f a.e. . If $\int g = \lim \int g_n$, then $\int f = \lim \int f_n$.

Canonical factorization of functions in H_ϕ or H_ϕ^+

The following canonical factorization theorem for functions in H_ϕ or H_ϕ^+ is an extension of those in [3] and [4] for N^+ and $H^p, 0 < p \leq 1$.

Canonical factorization theorem Let $f \in H_\phi$ be not identically zero. Then $f = Bg$, where B is a Blaschke product $g \in H_\phi$ is unique with no zeros in D and

$$(1) \|f\|_\phi \leq \|g\|_\phi \leq 2\|f\|_\phi$$

Moreover, if $f \in H_\phi^+$, then $g \in H_\phi^+$ and $\|g\|_\phi = \|f\|_\phi$.

Proof: First assume that f has infinitely many zeros $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \dots$ in D repeated according to their respective multiplicities and $\lambda_n \neq 0$ for all $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. Let

$$b_n(z) = \prod_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{|\lambda_j|}{\lambda_j}\right) \left(\frac{\lambda_j - z}{1 - \bar{\lambda}_j z}\right) \text{ and } g_n = \frac{f}{b_n}, n=1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Then $|b_n|$ is continuous on the closure \bar{D} of D and $\equiv 1$ on T . Thus for a fixed n and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, $|b_n(z)| > 1 - \varepsilon$ when $r = |z|$ is sufficiently close to 1. Hence,

$$(2) \phi(|g_n(re^{i\theta})|) = \phi\left(\left|\frac{f(re^{i\theta})}{b_n(re^{i\theta})}\right|\right) \leq \phi\left(\left|\frac{1}{1-\varepsilon} f(re^{i\theta})\right|\right) \leq \left(\frac{1}{1-\varepsilon} + 1\right)\phi(|f(re^{i\theta})|),$$

which implies that $\|g_n\|_\phi \leq 2\|f\|_\phi$, by integrating (2), letting $r \rightarrow 1^-$

and then $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$. Noting that $|g_n| = \left|\frac{f}{b_n}\right| \geq |f|$, we obtain

$$\|f\|_\phi \leq \|g_n\|_\phi \leq 2\|f\|_\phi.$$

The subharmonicity of $\phi(|g_n|)$ and $f(0) \neq 0$ give

$$0 < \phi\left(\left|\frac{f(0)}{\prod_{j=1}^n |\lambda_j|}\right|\right) = \phi(|g_n(0)|) \leq \int_T \phi(|(g_n)_r|) d\sigma \leq 2\|f\|_\phi$$

Therefore, for all $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, $\prod_{j=1}^n |\lambda_j| \geq \frac{|f(0)|}{\phi^{-1}(2\|f\|_\phi)} > 0$.

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ it follows that

$$(3) \prod_{j=1}^\infty |\lambda_j| \geq \frac{|f(0)|}{\phi^{-1}(2\|f\|_\phi)} > 0.$$

Thus, by [14, Theorem 15.5], (3) is equivalent to $\sum_{j=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_j|) < \infty$.

Hence,

$B(z) = \prod_{n=1}^\infty \left(\frac{|\lambda_n|}{\lambda_n}\right) \left(\frac{\lambda_n - z}{1 - \bar{\lambda}_n z}\right)$, $z \in D$ is a Blaschke product and $\{b_n\}$ converges uniformly on compact subsets of D to B . Therefore, [4, p. 56], $\{g_n\}$ converges uniformly on compact subsets of D to $g = \frac{f}{B}$.

Thus,

$$(4) \int_T \phi(|g_r|) d\sigma = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_T \phi(|(g_n)_r|) d\sigma \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|g_n\|_\phi \leq 2\|f\|_\phi.$$

Therefore, we obtain (1) from (4) and noting that $|g| \geq |f|$.

In case, $f \in H_\phi^+$ the dominated convergence theorem and (2) imply that

$$\|g_n\|_\phi = \lim_{r \rightarrow 1^-} \int_T \phi(|(g_n)_r|) d\sigma = \int_T \phi(|g_n|) d\sigma = \int_T \phi\left(\left|\frac{f}{b_n}\right|\right) d\sigma = \int_T \phi(|f|) d\sigma = \|f\|_\phi.$$

Also, by Fatou's lemma we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_\phi &= \int_T \phi(|f|) d\sigma = \int_T \lim_{r \rightarrow 1^-} \phi(|g_r|) d\sigma \leq \lim_{r \rightarrow 1^-} \int_T \phi(|g_r|) d\sigma = \|g\|_\phi \\ &= \lim_{r \rightarrow 1^-} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_T \phi(|(g_n)_r|) d\sigma \leq \lim_{r \rightarrow 1^-} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|g_n\|_\phi = \|f\|_\phi. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $g \in H_\phi^+$ and $\|f\|_\phi = \|g\|_\phi$.

The above argument easily shows that the same results hold when f has finitely many zeros in D or $f(0) = 0$. The uniqueness of g follows from properties of zeros of analytic functions.

The space $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ and its bounded subsets

As in H_ϕ , Λ and ϕ induce on $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ a quasi-norm $\| \cdot \|_{\phi,\Lambda}$ given by:

$$\|u\|_{\phi,\Lambda} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u)|), \forall u = (c_n(u)) \in \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$$

For notation convenience we write $\| \cdot \|_\phi$ instead of $\| \cdot \|_{\phi,\Lambda}$.

Theorem 3.1 *The space $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ is an F-space with the distance function σ defined by*

$$\sigma(u, v) = \|u - v\|_\phi, \forall u, v \in \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$$

That is,

- (i) $\sigma(u, v) = \sigma(u - v, 0)$
- (ii) *If $\sigma(u_k, u) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, then $\sigma(\alpha u_k, \alpha u) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ for all $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$.*
- (iii) *If $\alpha_k \rightarrow \alpha$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, then $\sigma(\alpha_k u, \alpha u) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ for all $u \in \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$*
- (iv) $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ is complete.

Proof: The linearity of $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ and (ii) follow from $\phi(|\alpha x|) \leq (|\alpha| + 1)\phi(x)$, $x \geq 0$, while (i) is obvious from the definition of σ . To prove (iii), let $u \in \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ be fixed. Then, for all $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\sum_{n=n_0+1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u)|) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$. Let $K > \max_{1 \leq n \leq n_0} |c_n(u)|$ and $0 < \delta_1 = \min\{1, \frac{1}{K} \phi^{-1}(\frac{\varepsilon}{2n_0})\}$. Then there exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $|\alpha_k - \alpha| < \delta_1$ for all $k \geq k_0$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(\alpha_k u, \alpha u) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|(\alpha_k - \alpha)c_n(u)|) \\ &\leq \sum_{n=1}^{n_0} \phi(K|\alpha_k - \alpha|) + \sum_{n=n_0+1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u)|) \\ &< \frac{\varepsilon}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} = \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

for all $k \geq k_0$. Thus, (ii) holds.

To prove (iv) let (u_k) be a Cauchy sequence in $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$. First we show that for each fixed $j \in \mathbb{N}$, the complex sequence $(c_j(u_k))$ is Cauchy. Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be given. Then there exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all k , we have

$$\sigma(u_k, u_m) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u_k) - c_n(u_m)|) < (1 - |\lambda_j|^2) \phi(\varepsilon)$$

Hence, for all $k, m \geq k_0$ we have $|c_j(u_k) - c_j(u_m)| < \varepsilon$, i. e., $(c_j(u_k))$ is Cauchy.

Let $c_n = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} c_n(u_k)$. For all $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $k_0 \in \mathbf{N}$ such that, for all $k, m \geq k_0$, we have

$$\sigma(u_k, u_m) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u_k) - c_n(u_m)|) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$$

Therefore, for each

$j \in \mathbf{N}$ and for all $k, m \geq k_0$ we have

$$\sum_{n=1}^j (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u_k) - c_n(u_m)|) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$$

Letting $m \rightarrow \infty$ and then $j \rightarrow \infty$, it follows that $u = (c_n) \in \ell_{\Lambda}(\phi)$ and $\sigma(u_k, u) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, $\ell_{\Lambda}(\phi)$ is complete.

In an F-space X with topology induced by a complete translation invariant metric ρ , there are two none equivalent notions of bounded sets. The first is in the metric sense, i.e., a subset E of X is ρ -bounded if there exists a constant M such that $\rho(x, y) \leq M < \infty$ for all $x, y \in E$. The second is in the topological vector space sense, i.e., a subset E of X is *topologically bounded* if for each neighborhood V of zero there exists a number $t_0 > 0$ such that $E \subseteq t V$ for all $t \geq t_0$. We refer the interested reader to [13].

The bounded subsets of N^+ and $\ell_{\mathbb{Z}}^+$ are studied by N. Yanagihara in [16]. When $\phi(ab) \leq \phi(a) + \phi(b)$ for all $a, b \geq 0$, his results about N^+ were generalized to H_{ϕ}^+ in [9] where it is shown that a subset E of H_{ϕ}^+ is topologically bounded iff $(\forall \varepsilon > 0 \exists \delta = \delta(\varepsilon) > 0$ such that for each subset A of T with $\sigma(A) < \delta$ we have $\int_A \phi(|f|) d\sigma < \varepsilon, \forall f \in E$).

Moreover, as a corollary of this, a necessary but not sufficient condition for topological bounded sets is given, namely if a subset E of H_{ϕ}^+ is topologically bounded, then there exists a positive continuous function $\omega(r)$, independent of $f \in E$, $\omega(r) \downarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow 1^-$, and such that

$$M(r, f) \leq \phi^{-1}\left(\frac{\omega(r)}{1-r}\right), \text{ for all } f \in E \text{ and } 0 < r < 1$$

$$\text{Where } M(r, f) = \max_{|z|=r} |f(z)|.$$

Here, we prove the corresponding results for $\ell_{\Lambda}(\phi)$.

Theorem 3.2 Let $\phi(ab) \leq \phi(a) + \phi(b)$ for all $a, b \geq 0$ and E be a subset of $\ell_{\Lambda}(\phi)$. Then E is topologically bounded iff

$$(i) \quad \|u\|_{\phi} < M = M(E) < \infty, \forall u \in E$$

And

$$(ii) \quad \forall \varepsilon > 0 \exists n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon, E) \in \mathbf{N} \text{ such that}$$

$$\sum_{n=n_0+1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u)|) < \varepsilon, \forall u = (c_n(u)) \in E$$

Proof: Assume that E is a topologically bounded subset of $\ell_{\Lambda}(\phi)$.

Therefore, $\forall \eta > 0, \exists \alpha = \alpha(\eta) > 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1$, such that $\beta E \subseteq V(\eta) = \{u \in \ell_\Lambda(\phi); \|u\|_\phi < \eta\}$ whenever $0 < \beta \leq \alpha$. Let $\eta = 1$. Then $\exists \alpha = \alpha(1), 0 < \alpha \leq 1$, such that $\beta E \subseteq V(1)$ whenever $0 < \beta \leq \alpha$.

Let $M = 1 + \lceil \frac{1}{\alpha} \rceil$. Then for all $u = (c_n(u)) \in E$, we have

$$\|u\|_\phi = \left\| \frac{1}{\alpha} \cdot \alpha u \right\|_\phi \leq \left(\left\lceil \frac{1}{\alpha} \right\rceil + 1 \right) \|\alpha u\|_\phi < \left(\left\lceil \frac{1}{\alpha} \right\rceil + 1 \right) = M$$

Thus, (i) holds.

Next, let $\varepsilon > 0$ be given. Choose η such that $0 < \eta < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ and $\alpha = \alpha(\eta)$ as above. Since $\sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) < \infty$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbf{N}$ such that

$$\sum_{n=n_0+1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) < (\varepsilon/2\phi(\alpha^{-1}))$$

Then, (ii) holds, since for all $u = (c_n(u)) \in E$ we have

$$\sum_{n=n_0+1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u)|) \leq \sum_{n=n_0+1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right) + \sum_{n=n_0+1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|\alpha c_n(u)|) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2} + \|\alpha u\|_\phi < \frac{\varepsilon}{2} + \eta < \varepsilon$$

Conversely, assume that (i) and (ii) hold. Let $V(\eta)$ be any neighborhood of zero. Continuity of ϕ at zero from the right implies that there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such $\varepsilon < \eta/2$ and $\phi(x) < \eta/2K$ whenever $0 \leq x < \varepsilon$ where

$$\sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) < \infty$$

Therefore, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbf{N}$ as in (ii). For each $u = (c_n(u)) \in E$, let

$$\delta = \min_{1 \leq n \leq n_0} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) > 0 \text{ and } A_u = \{n \in \mathbf{N}: \phi(|c_n(u)|) < \frac{M}{\delta}\}. \text{ Thus,}$$

$$M > \|u\|_\phi \geq \sum_{n \notin A_u} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u)|) \geq \frac{M}{\delta} \sum_{n \notin A_u} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2)$$

Hence, $\sum_{n \notin A_u} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) < \delta$. This implies that $\{1, 2, \dots, n_0\} \subseteq A_u$. Letting $0 < \alpha < \min\{1, \frac{\varepsilon}{2\phi^{-1}(M/\delta)}\}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\alpha u\|_\phi &\leq \sum_{n=1}^{n_0} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u)|) + \sum_{n=n_0+1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u)|) \\ &< \phi\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{n_0} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) + \varepsilon < \phi\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right) K + \frac{\eta}{2} < \eta \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\alpha E \subseteq V(\eta)$, which shows that E is topologically bounded.

Corollary 3.3 Let $\phi(ab) \leq \phi(a) + \phi(b)$, $a, b \geq 0$ and E be a topologically bounded subset of $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$. Then there exists a positive sequence (ω_n) , $\omega_n \downarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and

$$\phi|c_n(u)| \leq \phi^{-1}\left(\frac{\omega_n}{1 - |\lambda_n|^2}\right), \forall u = (c_n(u)) \in E \text{ and } \forall n \in \mathbf{N}$$

Proof: From the proof of theorem 3.2 it follows that, for all $\eta > 0$, there exists $\delta = \delta(\eta) > 0$ such that

$$(1 - |\lambda_n|)\phi(|c_n(u)|) \leq (1 - |\lambda_n|)\frac{M}{\delta} + \frac{\eta}{2}$$

for all $u = (c_n(u)) \in E$ and for all $n \in \mathbf{N}$.

Let (η_k) be a positive sequence with $\eta_k \downarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. Hence, for each $k \in \mathbf{N}$ there exists $\delta_k = \delta(\eta_k) > 0$ such that

$$(1 - |\lambda_n|)\phi(|c_n(u)|) \leq (1 - |\lambda_n|)\frac{M}{\delta_k} + \frac{\eta_k}{2}$$

for all $u = (c_n(u)) \in E$ and for all $n \in \mathbf{N}$

Choose a strictly increasing sequence (n_k) in \mathbf{N} such that $n_k \uparrow \infty$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ and

$$(1 - |\lambda_n|)\phi(|c_n(u)|) \leq (1 - |\lambda_n|)\frac{M}{\delta_k} + \frac{\eta_k}{2} < \frac{\eta_k}{2} + \frac{\eta_k}{2} = \eta_k$$

for all $n \geq n_k$ and for all $u = (c_n(u)) \in E$.

Define the positive sequence (ω_n) by:

$$\omega_n = \begin{cases} \frac{M}{\delta_1} + \eta_1, & 1 \leq n < n_1 \\ \eta_k, & n_k \leq n < n_{k+1}, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{cases}$$

Then, (ω_n) satisfies the required properties.

We mention that although the spaces H_ϕ^+ and $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ look similar, a topologically bounded subset of $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ could be relatively compact while a topologically bounded subset of H_ϕ^+ need not be relatively compact.

This is the case when $\phi(x) = \log(1 + x)$ as in [16].

Interpolation in H_ϕ and H_ϕ^+

The first result of this section is a generalization from N^+ [17, Theorem 1(second part)] to H_ϕ^+ while the second is a generalization from N [17, Theorem 4] to H_ϕ .

Theorem 4.1 If $\ell_\Lambda(\phi) \subseteq T(H_\phi^+)$, then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi\left(\frac{1}{|B_n(\lambda_n)|}\right) = 0$$

Where

$$B_n(z) = \prod_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq n}} |\lambda_m| \frac{\lambda_m - z}{1 - \bar{\lambda}_m z}, z \in D$$

Proof: Let $(K = \ker T = \{f \in H_\phi^+ : f(\lambda_n) = 0, \forall n \in \mathbf{N}\})$. Then K is a closed subspace of H_ϕ^+ since the convergence of a sequence in H_ϕ^+ implies its convergence on compact subsets of D . Thus, by [13, Theorem

1.41] the quotient space $H_\phi^+/K = \{f + K: f \in H_\phi^+\}$ is an F-space. Let ρ be the metric on H_ϕ^+/K and $\pi: H_\phi^+ \rightarrow H_\phi^+/K$ be the quotient map where $\pi(f) = f + K$ for all $f \in H_\phi^+$. For each $u = (c_n(u)) \in \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ there exists $f \in H_\phi^+$ such that $T f = (f(\lambda_n)) = u$.

Let $\tilde{T}u = \pi(f)$. Then it is easy to see that $\tilde{T}: \ell_\Lambda(\phi) \rightarrow H_\phi^+/K$ is a well defined linear operator. Using the closed graph theorem we prove that it is continuous and hence bounded (See [13]).

Let $u_k \rightarrow 0$ in $\ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ and $\tilde{T}u_k = \pi(f_k) \rightarrow \pi(f^*)$ in H_ϕ^+/K as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

We show that $f^* \in K$ i. e. $\pi(f^*) = K$

Let $Tf^* = (f^*(\lambda_n)) = (c_n)$, $Tf_k = (f_k(\lambda_n)) = (c_n(u_k)) = u_k$ and $n_0 \in \mathbf{N}$ be fixed. Then $\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists k_0, k_0 \in \mathbf{N}$ such that if $k \geq k_0$, then

$$\|u_k\|_\phi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u_k)|) < (1 - |\lambda_{n_0}|^2) \phi(\varepsilon)$$

Thus, if $k \geq k_0$, then $|f_k(\lambda_{n_0})| = |c_{n_0}(u_k)| < \varepsilon$. Therefore, $f_k(\lambda_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ for all $n \in \mathbf{N}$.

Also, $k \geq k_1$, then

$$\rho(\pi(f_k), \pi(f^*)) = \rho(\pi(f_k - f^*), \pi(0)) < \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$$

For each $k \geq k_1$, choose $g_k \in H_\phi^+$ such that $\pi(g_k) = \pi(f_k - f^*)$ and $\|g_k\|_\phi < \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$

(See [13, p. 30]). Thus, for each $k \geq k_1$ and $\forall n \in \mathbf{N}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|c_n(u_k) - c_n|) &= (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|f_k(\lambda_n) - f^*(\lambda_n)|) \\ &= (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(|g_k(\lambda_n)|) \leq 4 \|g_k\|_\phi < \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

Let $k \rightarrow \infty$ and then $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ we get $f^*(\lambda_n) = c_n = 0 \forall n \in \mathbf{N}$, i.e.,

$f^* \in K$.

Next, let $e_k = (c_n(e_k))$, where $c_n(e_k) = 1$ if $n = k$ and $c_n(e_k) = 0$ if $n \neq k$. Then $\|e_k\|_\phi = (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi(1) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, the continuity of \tilde{T} implies that $\rho(\pi(f_k), \pi(0)) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, where $\tilde{T}e_k = \pi(f_k)$ and $Tf_k = e_k$

Thus, $\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists k_2 \in \mathbf{N}$, such that if $k \geq k_2$, then $\rho(\pi(f_k), \pi(0)) < \varepsilon$.

For each $k \geq k_2$, choose $h_k \in H_\phi^+$ such that $\pi(h_k) = \pi(f_k)$ and $\|h_k\|_\phi < \varepsilon$.

Therefore, there exists a sequence (h_k) in H_ϕ^+ which converges to zero and $(h_k(\lambda_n)) = (f_k(\lambda_n))$ for all $k, n \in \mathbf{N}$. For $k > n$, let

$$B_{n,k}(z) = \prod_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq n}}^k \frac{|\lambda_m|}{\lambda_m} \frac{\lambda_m - z}{1 - \bar{\lambda}_m z} \text{ and } H_{n,k} = h_n / B_{n,k}.$$

Then, $H_{n,k} \in H_\phi^+$ and $\|H_{n,k}\|_\phi = \|h_n\|_\phi$. Hence,

$$(1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi\left(\frac{1}{|B_{n,k}(\lambda_n)|}\right) = (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) \phi\left(\frac{f_n(\lambda_n)}{|B_{n,k}(\lambda_n)|}\right)$$

$$= (1 - |\lambda_n|^2)\phi(|H_{n,k}(\lambda_n)|) \leq 4\|h_n\|_\phi$$

Letting $k \rightarrow \infty$ and then $n \rightarrow \infty$ we get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|^2)\phi\left(\frac{1}{|B_n(\lambda_n)|}\right) = 0$$

Theorem 4.2 Let (λ_n) be uniformly separated. Then $T(H_\phi) \subseteq \ell_\Lambda(\psi)$, where $\psi(x) = (\phi(x))^P$, $x \geq 0$ and $0 < P < 1$

Moreover, the above inclusion could be proper.

Proof: Let $f \in H_\phi$. Then $f = Bg$ where B is the Blaschke product of the zeros of f in D and $g \in H_\phi$ with no zeros in D . Let $h = u_g + iv_g$ where v_g is a harmonic conjugate of u_g the least harmonic majorant of $\phi(|g|)$. Since the analytic function h has a positive real part, then by [3, Theorem 3.2] $h \in H^P$, $0 < P < 1$. Then, $Th \in \ell_\Lambda^P$, $0 < P < 1$ (See [17, p. 429]). Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \|Tf\|_\psi &= \sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) (\phi(|f(\lambda_n)|))^P \leq \sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) (\phi(|g(\lambda_n)|))^P \\ &\leq \sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) (u_g(\lambda_n))^P \leq \sum_{n=1}^\infty (1 - |\lambda_n|^2) |h(\lambda_n)|^P < \infty \end{aligned}$$

Next, let $\lambda_n = 1 - b^n$ where $0 < b < 1$ and $(c_n) = (\phi^{-1}(n/b^n))$. Then, by [3, Theorem 9.2, p. 155] (λ_n) is uniformly separated and $\|(c_n)\|_\psi \leq 2 \sum_{n=1}^\infty b^n \left(\frac{n}{b^n}\right)^2 = 2 \sum_{n=1}^\infty n^2 b^{n(1-P)} < \infty$, i.e., $(c_n) \in \ell_\Lambda(\psi)$. Also,

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (1 - |\lambda_n|)\phi(|c_n|) = \infty$. Thus, there is no $f \in H_\phi$ such that $Tf = (c_n)$ since $(1 - |z|)\phi(|f(z)|) \leq 2\|f\|_\phi$, $\forall f \in H_\phi$ and $\forall z \in D$.

We note that $l^P \subseteq l^\infty \subseteq \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$, $0 < P < \infty$. Moreover, for each $f \in H_\phi^+$ we have [9, Theorem 2.1, p. 14] $\lim_{r \rightarrow 1^-} (1 - r)\phi(M(r, f)) = 0$.

Hence, it follows that $T_\phi H_\phi^+ \subseteq l^\infty$. Also, when $\phi(x) = x^P$, $0 < P \leq 1$, it is easy to see that

$$T_\phi(H_\phi^+) = l^P \text{ iff } T(H_\phi^+) = \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$$

Thus, in this case, theorem 9.1 in [3] can be restated as $T(H_\phi^+) = \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$ iff (λ_n) is uniformly separated. So, it is natural to ask for what other kinds of ϕ this is true. When $\phi(x) = \log(1 + x)$, it is shown [17, Theorem 3] that there exists a uniformly separated sequence (λ_n) and $f \in H_\phi^+$ such that $T(f) \notin \ell_\Lambda(\phi)$. Furthermore, if (λ_n) is uniformly separated, then $\ell_\Lambda(\phi) \subseteq T(H_\phi^+)$.

(See [17, Theorem 1]). This motivated the following theorem whose converse is still open.

Theorem 4.3 If $T_\phi(H_\phi^+) = l^P$, $0 < P \leq \infty$, $\phi(ab) \leq \phi(a) + \phi(b)$, $a, b \geq 0$, then (λ_n) is uniformly separated.

Proof: The closed graph theorem implies that $T_\phi: (H_\phi^+) \rightarrow \ell^P$ for $0 < P \leq \infty$ is continuous since $T_\phi(H_\phi^+) \subseteq \ell^P$. Then $K_\phi = \text{kernel of } T_\phi$ is a closed subspace of H_ϕ^+ and the quotient space H_ϕ^+/K_ϕ is an F-space. Since $T_\phi(H_\phi^+) = \ell^P$, T_ϕ induces a bijective bounded linear operator $\tilde{T}_\phi: H_\phi^+/K_\phi \rightarrow \ell^P$ such that $T_\phi = \tilde{T}_\phi \circ \pi$ where $\pi: H_\phi^+ \rightarrow H_\phi^+/K_\phi$ is the quotient map (see [13, p. 37]). The open mapping theorem [13] implies that $\tilde{T}_\phi^{-1}: \ell^P \rightarrow H_\phi^+/K_\phi$, the inverse of \tilde{T}_ϕ , is bounded, i.e., continuous. Let $e_k = (c_n(e_k))$ be as before and $E = \{e_k: k = 1, 2, \dots\}$. For each $k \in \mathbf{N}$ there exists $f_k \in H_\phi^+$ such that $T_\phi f_k = e_k$. Let $E_1 = \{f_k \in H_\phi^+: T_\phi f_k = e_k\}$ We prove that E_1 is a bounded subset of H_ϕ^+ . Let $V = V(\eta) = \{f \in H_\phi^+: \|f\|_\phi < \eta\}, \eta > 0$, be a neighborhood of zero in H_ϕ^+ . Since π and \tilde{T}_ϕ are open there exists $\alpha_1 > 0$ such that $W = \{u \in \ell^P: \|u\|_P < \alpha_1\} \subseteq (\tilde{T}_\phi \circ \pi)(V)$ (See [13]). Let $0 < \alpha < \min\{1, \alpha_1\}$. Then $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ and $\beta E \subseteq W$ whenever $0 < \beta \leq \alpha$. Thus, $\beta E \subseteq (\tilde{T}_\phi \circ \pi)(V) = T_\phi(V)$. Hence, $E \subseteq T_\phi(\frac{1}{\beta}V)$. Therefore,

$$\beta E_1 \subseteq \beta T_\phi^{-1}(E) \subseteq \beta T_\phi^{-1}(T_\phi(\frac{1}{\beta}V)) \subseteq V$$

whenever $0 < \beta \leq \alpha$. Thus E_1 is a topologically bounded subset of H_ϕ^+ . Clearly, $E_2 = \{f_n/B_{n,k}: n, k = 1, 2, \dots, k > n\}$ is bounded since $f_n/B_{n,k} \in H_\phi^+$ and $\|f_n/B_{n,k}\|_\phi = \|f_n\|_\phi$. Therefore, by [9, Corollary 3.2, p. 18], there exists a positive continuous function $\omega(r) \downarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow 1^2$ and

$$M(r, f_n/B_{n,k}) \leq \phi^{-1}\left(\frac{2\omega(r)}{1-r^2}\right)$$

$\forall r \in (0,1)$ and $\forall k, n \in \mathbf{N}$ where $k > n$. Since $r_n = |\lambda_n| \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbf{N}$ such that

$$\left| \frac{f_n(\lambda_n)}{B_{n,k}(\lambda_n)} \right| \leq M(r_n, f_n/B_{n,k}) \leq \phi^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{1-r^2}\right)$$

for all $n \geq n_0$. Thus,

$$\frac{1}{|B_{n,k}(\lambda_n)|} = \left| \frac{f_n(\lambda_n)}{\phi^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{1-r^2}\right) B_{n,k}(\lambda_n)} \right| \leq 1$$

For all $n \geq n_0$. If $|z| \leq r < 1$, then

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left| 1 - \left| \frac{z - \lambda_m}{1 - \bar{\lambda}_m z} \right| \right| \leq \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left| 1 - \frac{|\lambda_m|}{\lambda_m} \left(\frac{\lambda_m - z}{1 - \bar{\lambda}_m z} \right) \right| \leq \frac{2}{1-r} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - |\lambda_m|) < \infty$$

Therefore, by [14, Theorem 15.5], $|B_n(\lambda_n)| > 0$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots, n_0 - 1$. Let $\delta = \min_{1 \leq n \leq n_0-1} \{1, |B_n(\lambda_n)|\}$. Then (λ_n) is uniformly separated since $|B_n(\lambda_n)| \geq \delta > 0$ for all $n \in \mathbf{N}$.

Next we consider the relation between free interpolation and harmonic functions. Let $Har(D)$ denote the space of harmonic functions in D and $Har_+(D)$ the subspace of its positive functions.

When $\Lambda = (\lambda_n)$ is a sequence in D such that $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty}(1 - |\lambda_n|) < \infty$ we define $\ell_\phi = \{(c_n): \exists h \in Har_+(D) \text{ such that } \phi(|c_n|) \leq h(\lambda_n), n = 1,2,3,\dots\}$

and

$$\ell_\phi^+ = \{(c_n): \exists \text{ aquasi-bounded } h \in Har_+(D) \text{ such that } \phi(|c_n|) \leq h(\lambda_n), n = 1,2,3,\dots\}$$

The main results of A. Hartmann [5] is giving equivalent conditions for free interpolation in N and N^+ depending on the canonical factorization of functions in them in terms of Blaschke products, singular inner functions and outer functions which is not available in H_ϕ and H_ϕ^+ in general. Also, in [6] he defined big Hardy-Orlicz spaces and characterized free interpolation in them. Here we prove the following results noting that, according to his results, when $\phi(x) = \log(1 + x)$, equivalence holds in theorem 4.4(i) and (iii) below.

Theorem 4.4 Let $\phi(sb) \leq \phi(a) + \phi(b)$, $a, b \geq 0$

- (i) If $\ell_\phi = (H_\phi|\Lambda)$, then $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi)$
- (ii) If $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi)$, then $(H_\phi|\Lambda) \subseteq l_\phi$
- (iii) If $\ell_\phi^+ = (H_\phi^+|\Lambda)$, then $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi^+)$
- (iv) If $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi^+)$, then $(H_\phi^+|\Lambda) \subseteq l_\phi^+$
- (v) Let $\phi(x) = \psi(\log(1 + x))$, $x \geq 0$, where ψ is a modulus function.

If $\Lambda \in Int(N)$, then $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi)$. Moreover, If $\Lambda \in Int(N^+)$, then $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi^+)$

Proof:

- (i) Assume that $\ell_\phi = (H_\phi|\Lambda)$ and $(c_n) \in l^\infty$. Then there exists a positive constant c such that $\phi(|c_n|) \leq \phi(c) < \infty$, $n = 1,2,3,\dots$. Therefore, $(c_n) \in \ell_\phi = (H_\phi|\Lambda)$. This implies that $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi)$ since $l^\infty \subseteq (H_\phi|\Lambda)$
- (ii) Assume that $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi)$ and $(c_n) \in (H_\phi|\Lambda)$. Then there exists $f \in H_\phi$ such that $(c_n)(f(\lambda_n))$. Let $h = u_f$. Then $\phi(|c_n|) = \phi(|f(\lambda_n)|) \leq h(\lambda_n)$, $n = 1,2,3,\dots$. Therefore, $(H_\phi|\Lambda) \subseteq l_\phi$

The proof of (iii) and (iv) is similar to (i) and (ii).

For (v) the inequalities $x \leq 1 + [x] \leq 1 + x$, $x \geq 0$ imply that $\psi(x) \leq \psi(1)(1 + x)$, $x \geq 0$.

Hence, $\phi(x) = \psi(\log(1 + x)) \leq \psi(1)(\log(1 + x))$, $x \geq 0$. Thus,

$$N \subseteq H_\phi \text{ and } N^+ \subseteq H_\phi^+.$$

which implies (v).

Finally under certain constraints on ϕ we get the following results.

Theorem 4.5 Let $\phi(ab) \leq \phi(a) + \phi(b)$, $a, b \geq 0$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\phi(x)}{\log x} = \alpha$

- (i) If $\alpha \in (0, \infty)$, then $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi)$ iff $\Lambda \in Int(N)$ and $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi^+)$ iff $\Lambda \in Int(N^+)$
- (ii) If $\alpha = \infty$, then $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi) \Rightarrow \Lambda \in Int(N)$ and $\Lambda \in Int(H_\phi^+) \Rightarrow \Lambda \in Int(N^+)$

(iii) If $\alpha = 0$, then $\Lambda \in \text{Int}(N) \Rightarrow \Lambda \in \text{Int}(H_\phi)$ and $\Lambda \in \text{Int}(N^+) \Rightarrow \Lambda \in \text{Int}(H_\phi^+)$

Proof:

(i) Let $\alpha \in (0, \infty)$. Then there exists $x_0 > 1$ such that $\frac{\alpha}{2} \log x < \phi(x) < \frac{3\alpha}{2} \log x$, for all $x \geq x_0$.

Hence,

$$\log(1+x) \leq 1 + \log^+ x = 1 + \log x \leq 1 + \frac{2}{\alpha} \phi(x), \text{ for all } x \geq x_0.$$

Thus,

$$\log(1+x) \leq 1 + \log(1+x_0) + \frac{2}{\alpha} \phi(x), \text{ for all } x \geq 0,$$

implies that $H_\phi \subseteq N$ and $H_\phi^+ \subseteq N^+$. Also, we have

$$\phi(x) \leq \frac{3\alpha}{2} \log(1+x) + \phi(x_0), \text{ for all } x \geq 0$$

implies that $N \subseteq H_\phi$ and $N^+ \subseteq H_\phi^+$. Therefore, (i) holds since $N = H_\phi$ and $N^+ = H_\phi^+$.

(ii) Let $\alpha = \infty$. Then there exists $x_0 > 1$ such that $\log x < \phi(x)$, for all $x \geq x_0$.

Hence,

$$\log(1+x) \leq 1 + \log(1+x_0) + \phi(x), \text{ for all } x \geq 0.$$

Thus, $H_\phi \subseteq N$ and $H_\phi^+ \subseteq N^+$ which implies (ii).

(iii) Let $\alpha = 0$. Then there exists $x_0 > 1$ such that $(x) < \log x$, for all $x \geq x_0$.

Hence,

$$\phi(x) < \log x < \log(1+x) < \log(1+x_0) + \log(1+x), \text{ for all } x \geq 0.$$

Thus, $N \subseteq H_\phi$ and $N^+ \subseteq H_\phi^+$ which implies (iii)

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